

Studies on 4-Hydroxybenzophenone and its Methyl Ether

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4-Hydroxybenzophenone has been chloromethylated and the product converted into the 3-formyl derivative by Sommelet reaction and into the known 3,4-dihydroxybenzophenone by Dakin oxidation. The former has been converted into 2'-hydroxy-5'-benzoylflavone through the intermediate chalcone obtained by condensation with 2-hydroxyacetophenone and into 6-benzoylcoumarin through Perkin acetylation and through Knoevenagel reaction with diethyl malonate. 4-Methoxybenzophenone has been similarly chloromethylated to 3-chloromethyl derivative and the product subjected to Sommelet reaction. The 3-formyl derivative obtained has been used as an intermediate for the synthesis of some flavone derivative¹.

A systematic study of the biphenyl derivatives is being made in these laboratories and as an extension of this study it was thought of interest to see the behaviour of benzophenone derivatives in various reactions and to synthesise oxygen heterocycles from them. The present study deals with 4-hydroxybenzophenone and its methyl ether.

4-Hydroxybenzophenone on chloromethylation with formalin in acetic acid medium afforded the 3-chloromethyl derivative which was converted to the 3-formyl derivative. 4-Methoxybenzophenone on chloromethylation in the presence of zinc chloride also gave the 3-chloromethyl derivative which on Sommelet reaction was converted into 3-formyl-4-methoxybenzophenone, identical with the product obtained on the methylation of the 3-formyl-4-hydroxybenzophenone, described above. The chloromethyl derivatives with sodium acetate and acetic acid furnished the corresponding acetoxymethyl derivatives, and with 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine sparingly soluble mono-2, 4-dinitrophenyl hydrazones. On Dakin oxidation, 3-formyl-4-hydroxybenzophenone afforded 3,4-dihydroxybenzophenone which gave green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride and was identical with the product obtained from Fries migration of catechol dibenzoate¹.

3-Formyl-4-hydroxybenzophenone on condensation with 2-hydroxyacetophenone in the presence of alcoholic potassium hydroxide furnished 2,2'-dihydroxy-5-benzoylchalcone (I, R = R' = H). It gave red colouration with sulphuric acid and reddish brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. On methylation it gave a dimethyl ether. The chalcone derivative was converted into 2'-hydroxy-5'-benzoylflavone (II, R = R' = H) by refluxing with selenium dioxide in iso-amyl alcohol. Similarly 2'-methoxy-5'-benzoylflavone (II, R = CH₃, R' = H) and 2',7-dimethoxy-5'-benzoylflavone (II, R = CH₃, R' = OCH₃) were synthesised from 3-formyl-4-methoxybenzophenone by successive condensation with 2-hydroxy- and 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyacetophenone respectively and subsequent isomerization and dehydrogenation of the chalcone derivatives.

3-Formyl-4-hydroxybenzophenone on condensation with diethyl malonate in the presence of a few drops of piperidine furnished ethyl-6-benzoylcoumarin-3-carboxylate

¹, Rosenblatt, Epstein and Levitet. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 75, 3277.

(III, R = COOEt). which on alkaline hydrolysis gave 3-carboxy-6-benzoylcoumarin (III R=COOH). The acid on decarboxylation with copper and quinoline afforded 6-benzoylcoumarin (III, R = H), identical in all respects with the compound obtained on Perkin acetylation of 3-formyl-4-hydroxybenzophenone.

EXPERIMENTAL*

3-Chloromethyl-4-hydroxybenzophenone.—HCl gas was passed through a mixture of formaldehyde (40%; 5 ml.), conc. HCl (10 ml.) and 1-hydroxybenzophenone (4.0 g.) in acetic acid (20 ml.), at room temperature for 2 hr. The chloromethyl derivative which separated was filtered, washed with acetic acid (10 ml.) and then with water and finally crystallised from benzene. Yield 3.2 g., m.p. 156° (decomp.) (Found: C = 68.27; H = 4.16; Cl = 14.3. $C_{14}H_{11}O_2Cl$ requires C=68.3; H = 4.5; Cl = 14.4%)

The acetoxy-methyl derivative.—3-Chloromethyl-4-hydroxybenzophenone (0.5 g.) in glacial acetic acid (7 ml.) was refluxed with fused sodium acetate (0.3 g.) for 1 hr. The acetoxy-methyl derivative which separated on pouring the reaction mixture into water was crystallised from dilute alcohol, and had m.p. 117°. (Found: C = 71.49; H = 5.51. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3$ requires C = 71.09; H = 5.22%.)

3-Formyl-4-hydroxybenzophenone.—3-Chloromethyl derivative (2 g.) in glacial acetic acid (15 ml.) was heated on a steam bath with hexamethylenetetramine (4 g.) for 2 hr. Dilute HCl (25 ml.; 1 : 1) was added to the mixture and the heating continued for 1 hr. more. It was then diluted with water and the separated formyl derivative was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in fine needles, m.p. 92°. Yield 0.5 g. (Found: C = 74.31; H = 3.98. $C_{14}H_{10}O_3$ requires C=74.33; H=4.4%.)

The mono-2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone.—It was crystallised from acetic acid, and had m.p. 253°. (Found: N = 14.3. $C_{20}H_{14}O_6N_4$ requires N = 13.8%.)

3-Chloromethyl-4-methoxybenzophenone.—On passing HCl gas at 60° through the clear mixture of 4-methoxy-benzophenone (4 g.), formaldehyde (40%; 5 ml.), conc. HCl (8 ml.), zinc chloride (3.0 g.) and acetic acid (15 ml.) for 2 hr., an oily product separated. The mixture was then diluted with water and extracted with ether. The product obtained

*All the melting points are uncorrected.

after removal of ether was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture. It had m.p. 99-100°, yield 3.5 g. (Found: C = 68.79; H = 4.99; Cl = 13.31. $C_{13}H_{13}O_2Cl$ requires C = 69.1; H = 5.02; Cl = 13.6%.)

The acetoxyethyl derivative.—This was prepared from the above chloromethyl derivative as before, crystallised from dilute alcohol, and had m.p. 94-95°. (Found: C = 71.71; H = 5.69; $C_{17}H_{16}O_4$ requires C = 71.8; H = 5.67%.)

3-Formyl -4-methoxybenzophenone.—3-Chloromethyl -4-methoxybenzophenone (2 g.) was added to the solution of hexamine (4 g.) in glacial acetic acid (15 ml.) and the mixture was heated on a steam bath for 3 hr. Dilute HCl (25 ml.; 1:1) was then added and the heating continued for 1 hr. more. The formyl derivative separated on cooling. It recrystallised from dil. alcohol in yellow needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 132-33°. (Found: C = 74.94; H = 4.83. $C_{15}H_{11}O_3$ requires C = 74.99; H = 5.05%.) Alexander³ who prepared it by a different method gives m.p. 134-35°.

The mono-2, 4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone: This was prepared as usual and crystallised from acetic acid, and had m.p. 250°. (Found: N = 13.3. $C_{21}H_{16}O_6N_4$ requires N = 13.74%.)

The same product was obtained when 3-formyl -4-hydroxy-benzophenone was methylated with dimethyl sulphate in acetone solution in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate.

3:4-Dihydroxybenzophenone.—To the clear solution of 3-formyl -4-hydroxybenzophenone (0.5 g.) in 10% sodium hydroxide (15 ml.) 1 cc. of H_2O_2 (100 vol.) was added and the mixture was stirred for 2 hr. at room temperature. The reaction mixture was filtered, cooled and acidified with HCl. It was then extracted with ether and the product obtained after removal of ether was crystallised from water (0.2 g.) and kept over conc. H_2SO_4 for 24 hr. It had m.p. 133-34°. The mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen prepared according to Rosenblatt, *et al.*² was not depressed. They reported m.p. 147°. Rozhdstvenski² reported m.p. 134° after drying over conc. H_2SO_4 .

2:2'-Dihydroxy-5-benzoylchalcone.—To a mixture of 3-formyl -4-hydroxybenzophenone (1 g.) and 2-hydroxy acetophenone (1 g.) dissolved in sufficient ethanol, KOH (3 g.; in 3 ml. H_2O) was added and the mixture left for 24 hr. It was then diluted and acidified with HCl. The precipitated chalcone derivative was crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 192-94°. It gave a reddish brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C = 77.23; H = 4.65. $C_{22}H_{16}O_4$ requires C = 76.74; H = 4.66%.)

2,2'-Dimethoxy-5-benzoylchalcone.—2,2'-Dihydroxy-5-benzoylchalcone (0.5 g.) was refluxed with dimethyl sulphate (1 g.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (2.5 g.) in acetone for 16 hr. The product obtained was crystallised from alcohol, and had m.p. 100°. (Found: C = 77.15; H = 5.57. $C_{24}H_{20}O_4$ requires C = 77.39; H = 5.41%.)

2'-Hydroxy-5-benzoylflavone.—2,2'-Dihydroxy-5-benzoylchalcone (1 g.) was refluxed with selenium dioxide (2 g.) in isoamyl alcohol (10 ml.) for 10 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and the flavone derivative (0.3 g.) separating on cooling was crystallised from alcohol. It had m.p. 263-65°. (Found: C = 77.53; H = 4.47. $C_{22}H_{14}O_4$ requires C = 77.2; H = 4.12%.)

2. Rozhdstvenski, *J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 46, 1075; *Chem. Abs.*, 1915, 9, 1899.

3. Alexander, *Rozzviki Chem.*, 1962, 38, 921; *Chem. Abs.*, 1963, 59, 3811.

2-Methoxy-5-benzoyl-2'-hydroxychalkone.—To 3-Formyl-4-methoxybenzophenone (1 g.) and 2-hydroxyacetophenone (1 g.) in alcohol, potassium hydroxide (3 g. in 3 ml. H_2O) was added and the clear reaction mixture was kept overnight. The chalkone obtained on acidification after dilution with water was crystallised from ethyl alcohol in yellow needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 134-35°. (Found: C = 77.07; H = 4.88. $C_{23}H_{18}O_4$ requires C = 77.07; H = 5.07%.) It gave a reddish brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

On methylation with dimethyl sulphate and potassium carbonate in acetone it gave 2, 2'-dimethoxy-5-benzoylchalkone, m.p. 100°. Mixed m.p. with the chalkone described earlier was not depressed.

2'-Methoxy-5'-benzoylflavone.—2-Methoxy-5-benzoyl-2'-hydroxy chalkone (1 g.) was refluxed with selenium dioxide (1.5 g.) in isoamyl alcohol (10 ml.) at 140-50° for 10 hr. The flavone derivative was crystallised from alcohol and had m.p. 163-64°. Yield 0.4 g. (Found: C = 77.53; H = 4.86. $C_{23}H_{18}O_4$ requires C = 77.52; H = 4.52%.)

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was prepared by refluxing the clear mixture of the above flavone derivative with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in alcohol for 2 hr. and crystallised from acetic acid. It had m.p. 265°. (Found: N = 10.55. $C_{29}H_{20}O_7N_4$ requires N = 10.25%.)

2,4'-dimethoxy-5-benzoyl-2'-hydroxychalkone.—3-Formyl-4-methoxy benzophenone (1 g.) in alcohol was condensed with 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyacetophenone (1 g.) in the presence of KOH (3 g. in 3 ml H_2O) and the reaction mixture worked up as before. Yield 0.6 g. (from alcohol), m.p. 143-44°. (Found: C = 74.22; H = 5.06. $C_{24}H_{20}O_5$ requires C = 74.2; H = 5.10%.) It gave reddish brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

On methylation in acetone solution with dimethyl sulphate in presence of potassium carbonate, it gave 2,2',4-trimethoxy-5-benzoylchalkone, m.p. 151-52°. (Found: C = 74.74; H = 5.9. $C_{25}H_{22}O_5$ requires C = 74.63; H = 5.52%.)

7,2'-Dimethoxy-5'-benzoylflavone.—A mixture of 2,4'-dimethoxy-5-benzoyl-2'-hydroxy chalkone (1 g.), selenium dioxide (2 g.) and isoamyl alcohol was refluxed for 10. hr. The product obtained was crystallised from alcohol and had m.p. 173°. (Found: C = 74.39; H = 5.09. $C_{24}H_{18}O_5$ requires C = 74.59; H = 4.60%.)

Ethyl-6-benzoylcoumarin-3-carboxylate.—A mixture of 3-formyl-4-hydroxybenzophenone (2 g.), diethylmalonate (2 g.) and a few drops of piperidine was kept at room temperature for 96 hr. It was then washed several times with petroleum ether and then with dil. HCl. The product obtained was crystallised from dil. alcohol. Yield 1.3 g. m.p. 173°. (Found: C = 70.53; H = 4.43. $C_{19}H_{14}O_5$ requires C = 70.79; H = 4.38%.)

6-Benzoylcoumarin-3-carboxylic Acid.—The above ester was heated with 10% sodium hydroxide solution on a steam bath till the reaction mixture became clear. The product obtained on acidification was crystallised from benzene in white needles, m.p. 202°. (Found: C = 69.36; H = 3.18. $C_{17}H_{10}O_5$ requires C = 69.39; H = 3.42%.)

6-Benzoylcoumarin.—The above acid (0.5 g.) was decarboxylated by refluxing with quinoline and copper powder for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and treated with dil. HCl. The product obtained was crystallised from dil. alcohol in shining yellow

needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 140-41°. (Found : C = 76.85 ; H = 3.87. $C_{16}H_{10}O_2$ requires C = 76.83 ; H = 4.03%.)

The same compound was obtained when a mixture of 3-formyl -4-hydroxybenzophenone (2 g.), acetic anhydride (2 ml.) and freshly fused sodium acetate (1 g.) was refluxed in an oil bath at 180° for 8 hr. The reaction mixture was then added to crushed ice and 6-benzoylcoumarin (0.6 g.) obtained was crystallised from dil. alcohol. Melting point and mixed m.p. with the above compound was not depressed.

The 2, 4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone was prepared as usual and crystallised from acetic acid. It had m.p. 253°. (Found : N = 13.22. $C_{12}H_8O_6N_2$ requires N = 13.02%.)

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